

Thomas of Aquinas and Boethius of Dacia on the Eternity of the World

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Abstract

This article deals with the question of the eternity of the world in the works of two authors from the thirteenth century, Thomas Aquinas (ca. 1225–1274) and Boethius of Dacia (d. ca. 1280). It is an analysis of their views in two works which share the same name: De Aeternitate Mundi. The analysis is appropriate because of the chronology and the political circumstances they share. Namely, both works were written around the year 1270, at the time of the debate over the appropriation of the newly introduced Greco-Islamic knowledge, which led to frequent condemnations by the Church. After giving a general introduction about the topic of the paper and the works analysed (including the main historiographical debates), each of them will be given a thorough examination. This examination will take into consideration the text structure, the different arguments presented therein, and the relevant secondary literature. Finally, possible answers to the questions posed in the Introduction: Firstly, can philosophy prove that the world was created in time?, and, secondly, Could God have created the world as eternal? will be given in the Conclusion, according to the views of the aforementioned authors.

Keywords: Thomas Aquinas – Boethius of Dacia – Eternity of the World – Medieval Philosophy – History of Philosophy

Introduction

After Aristotle's texts started getting translated into Latin in the second half of the twelfth century, from Arabic and Greek, various questions occurred when it came to “appropriating” Aristotle and the Catholic dogma and tradition in the Latin West. The understanding of Aristotle’s *Metaphysica* and the *Logica nova* was an easier task, especially when it came to the identification of Aristotle's Prime Mover with the Christian God.⁴⁸² However, it seemed that some theories of Aristotle that generally belong to his philosophy of nature were at direct odds with the Catholic teaching. One of these was Aristotle's position that the physical world and all the matter contained in it was eternal (existed forever), which he expounded in his *Physica*.⁴⁸³ At face value, this theory directly contradicts the Genesis creation story, in which God⁴⁸⁴ creates the material world out of nothing (*ex nihilo*).⁴⁸⁵ Among others, this must have been the reason behind the frequent condemnations of Aristotle’s doctrines (especially those pertaining to his philosophy of nature) throughout the thirteenth century.⁴⁸⁶ The most famous condemnation was that of 1277 in Paris, when bishop Etienne Tempier (d. 1279) issued 219 theses, out of which at least five had directly attacked the view that the world and matter contained in it are eternal.⁴⁸⁷ However, as Pearl Kibre and Nancy G. Siraisi point out, even though Aristotle’s natural philosophy was formally condemned throughout the thirteenth century, he was widely read, studied, and soon considered “the Philosopher” (e.g. in Oxford and Paris).⁴⁸⁸ This essay will deal with the eternity of the world, a particular thesis mentioned both in the 1270 and the 1277 Condemnations. More precisely, the views on the eternity of the world of two philosophers from the thirteenth century, Thomas Aquinas (d. 1274) and Boethius of Dacia (d. ca. 1280) will be analysed.⁴⁸⁹ After the *Introduction*, a

⁴⁸² Cf. Michael Camille, “Illustrations in Harley MS 3487 and the Perception of Aristotle's Libri Naturales in Thirteenth-Century England,” In *England in the Thirteenth Century: Proceedings of the 1984 Harlaxton Symposium*, ed. W.M. Ormrod (Suffolk, 1986), 37.

⁴⁸³ *Physics* I, 7.

⁴⁸⁴ In this work I chose to capitalise the *nomen sacrum* of the Christian Triune God, and His actions (so as to differentiate them from human actions), since it is capitalised both in the primary sources used, and in all of the secondary literature.

⁴⁸⁵ *Genesis* I, 1.

⁴⁸⁶ Firstly in 1210 and 1215, then in 1231 and in the famous condemnations of the bishop of Paris Etienne Tempier in 1270 and 1277. In this work, I will not be dealing with the political circumstances of the debate, nor the transmission of the translations of Greek sources. This is because my goal is primarily that of analysing the arguments themselves, rather than of what made them possible in the first place. For a succinct overview of the political issues involved with the condemnations, please refer to Fernand von Steenberghen, *The Philosophical Movement in the Thirteenth Century* (Edinburgh: Nelson, 1995), 45-46.

⁴⁸⁷ Cf. e.g. 52nd, 87th, 93rd, 98th, and 107th propositions, Edward Grant, *A Source Book in Medieval Science* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1974), 12-13.

⁴⁸⁸ Kibre, Pearl and Nancy G. Siraisi, “The Institutional Settings: The Universities” in *Science in the Middle Ages*, ed. D. C. Lindberg: 133.

⁴⁸⁹ The primary sources used are the translations of Aquinas’ and Boethius’ homonymous *opusculae* entitled *De Aeternitate Mundi*, using Miller’s and Wippel’s translations, respectively. Cf. Robert T. Miller, trans., “On the Eternity of the World,” Fordham University, <https://sourcebooks.fordham.edu/basis/aquinas-eternity.asp#f1> and trans. John F. Wippel, *On the Supreme Good: On the Eternity of the World; On Dreams* (Toronto: Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies, 1987).

general background of the question at hand and a short discussion about the proposed chronological dates of their writing will be discussed. Following this a detailed study of each work will be given. In the conclusion, I will give possible answers to these two research questions.

1. Can philosophy prove that the world was created in time?
2. Could God have created the world as eternal?

An Overview of the Problem

In the *Timaeus*, which was available in the Latin speaking world through Calcidius' fourth century translation alongside his commentary, Plato differentiates between two kinds of eternity, *aeternitas* (a-temporal eternity) and *aevum* (temporal eternity).⁴⁹⁰ In order to properly understand the eternity of celestial bodies and angels, Augustine of Hippo (354–430) added a third category of duration, which was outside of time, but not a-temporal.⁴⁹¹ Boethius (d. 524) contrasted the a-temporal simultaneously full and perfect possession of interminable life which pertains solely to God with the temporal (eternal or finite) duration which pertains to all other beings. Most early medieval authors, such as John Scotus Eriugena (ca. 800 - ca. 877), held a threefold differentiation of duration.⁴⁹² Namely, between eternal, which did not have a beginning or an end, perpetual, having a beginning, but not an end, and temporal, having both a beginning and an end. This threefold differentiation minimised Boethius' distinction between the a-temporal God and the temporal creation, thus laying the ground for the frequent late-medieval (Scholastic) understanding of all three levels (eternal, perpetual, and temporal) as existing on the same ontological level, something Boethius would have rejected.⁴⁹³

By the beginning of the thirteenth century, the terminology was further complicated by the circulation of two other terms, *saeculum* and *sempiternitas*, which both had roughly the same meaning as Plato's (i.e. Calcidius') *aevum*.⁴⁹⁴ Therefore, the complexity of terminology was very apparent by the second half of the 13th century. As was mentioned in the introduction of this article the idea of the world's eternity was a much debated topic in the 13th century, as seen by the frequent condemnations of that view. Dales speculates that Bonaventure of Bagnoregio (1221–1274) was the one who stirred up a lot of the inimical polemics that would follow, by announcing that such a view (i.e. the possibility of eternal creation) could not reasonably be held.⁴⁹⁵ In essence, there

⁴⁹⁰ Cf. Richard C. Dales, "Time and Eternity in the Thirteenth Century," *Journal of the History of Ideas* 49, no. 1 (1988): 27

⁴⁹¹ Dales, "Time and Eternity," 28.

⁴⁹² In his *De divisione naturae* written in the 860s.

⁴⁹³ Dales, "Time and Eternity," 29.

⁴⁹⁴ Dales, "Time and Eternity," 30.

⁴⁹⁵ Cf. Richard C. Dales, "Early Latin Discussions of the Eternity of the World in the Thirteenth Century," *Traditio* 43 (1987): 197.

were two questions that were at issue, the first of the relationship between time and eternity, and the second of the possibility of an eternally created world.⁴⁹⁶ The first question relates to the possibility of God, being a-temporal, relating to the temporal realm. In other words, how is God's "now" compatible with the temporal "now" that humans experience? The second question is related to the possibility of the world being created eternally. Here it is important to note that the world being created in time, but existing eternally in the future, was not accepted by any author of this period. This is because it would directly contradict the Christian teaching of the Last Judgement. Within the second question, which is the topic of our present study, the two main positions regarding the approach of reason⁴⁹⁷ to the eternity of the world were: 1. That the finite (or non-eternal) creation of the world is demonstrable by reason, and 2. That reason cannot prove that the world must have been created neither as eternal nor as finite.⁴⁹⁸ The main protagonists of the first view were St. Bonaventure, Henry of Ghent (1217–1293), and John Peckham (ca. 1230–1292).⁴⁹⁹ Who, and in which way exactly, falls under the second view, is very much a question of debate. Be that as it may, after the 1250s, the question of the possibility of eternal creation was much discussed, as seen from the writings of Henry of Ghent, Godfrey of Fontaines (d. 1309), Giles of Rome (1243–1316) and others.⁵⁰⁰

The answer to this possibility seems to have expanded further from the bounds of philosophical argumentation. In other words, the answer to this and other questions (such as there being only one active intellect in all humans) was also an answer to the acceptance or rejection of new Greek and Islamic influence, and the general relationship between philosophy and theology.⁵⁰¹ That could be the reason that Boethius of Dacia, as will be seen below, discusses the general relation between faith and reason (and subsequently theology and philosophy) within the treatise on the eternity of the world. In any case, according to their attitude both toward particular philosophical questions, the relationship between philosophy and theology, and to the acceptance or rejection of Aristotle, Steenberghen has differentiated three groups emerging within this debate, the "extreme left" of the "radical Aristotelians" (most prominently the faculty of arts masters Siger

⁴⁹⁶ Dales, "Early Discussions," 195.

⁴⁹⁷ By "reason" here it is meant that specifically human faculty which differentiates the species "human" from all other species and by which humans are able to do such things as form concepts and infer conclusions from premises. For an introduction to the Scholastic meaning of human rational faculties (such as *ratio*, *cognitio*, and *intellectus*), cf. Deborah L. Black, "The Nature of Intellect," in *The Cambridge History of Medieval Philosophy*, ed. Robert Pasnau (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010), 320-334.

⁴⁹⁸ Cf. Luca Bianchi, *L'errore di Aristotele: La Polemica Contro L'eternità Del Mondo Nel XIII Secolo* (Florence: Nuova Italia, 1984), 166.

⁴⁹⁹ John F. Wippel, "Introduction," in *On the Supreme Good: On the Eternity of the World; On Dreams*, ed. John F. Wippel (Toronto: Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies, 1987), 15.

⁵⁰⁰ John F. Wippel, "Did Thomas Aquinas Defend the Possibility of an Eternally Created World? (The De Aeternitate Mundi Revisited)," *Journal of the History of Philosophy* 19, no. 1 (1981): 22.

⁵⁰¹ Bianchi, *L'errore*, 164.

of Brabant and Boethius of Dacia), the “extreme right“ of the Theology masters (John Peckham, Henry of Ghent) and the Thomistic tradition in the middle (Thomas and his inheritors, such as Giles of Rome or Peter of Auvergne).⁵⁰²

When it comes to the life and works of Boethius of Dacia, our knowledge is very scarce. The only things we know for certain is that he was of Danish origin, became a Dominican friar later in life, and died probably around 1280.⁵⁰³ The dating of the *Liber de concordia fidei christianae et philosophiae de aeternitate mundi* – the full name of the treatise, which is also indicative of its content⁵⁰⁴ – is likewise not certain. Weisheipl thinks it cannot be placed “better than in 1270”.⁵⁰⁵ This view, however, is no longer taken as a fact, especially with the existence of Mowbray's articles.⁵⁰⁶

It does not seem important to go over Thomas Aquinas' biography, since much has been written about it, and it does not directly touch on our topic.⁵⁰⁷ However, a couple of short remarks will have to be said with regards to the historiographical debate over the datation of Thomas' *De Aeternitate Mundi* and the general character of the work. After Mandonnet's *Des écrits authentiques de S. Thomas d'Aquin* from 1910, and Grabmann's *Thomas von Aquin. Eine Einführung in seine Persönlichkeit und Gedankenwelt* from 1912, most of historiography after Mandonnet and Grabmann (pace Pelster)⁵⁰⁸ before Bukowski's 1970 article *An Early Dating for Aquinas' 'De aeternitate mundi'*, accepted 1270–1272 as the timeframe for the writing of the treatise. Bukowski's argument relies on the analysis of certain phrases in Thomas' *De Aeternitate Mundi* which purports to show that *De Aeternitate Mundi* is closer to his *Scriptum super librum Sentiarum* (written in the 1250s) than the *Summa Theologiae* (began in 1265). What Bukowski draws from this is that *De Aeternitate Mundi* is an earlier and less developed work, whereas the ideas are further elaborated in the *Summa Theologiae*. The second argument is the debate with Bonaventure which must have taken place in the 1250s, and not later. Therefore, Bukowski asks, why would Thomas have waited twenty years for the response?⁵⁰⁹

⁵⁰² Cf. Steenberghen, *The Philosophical Movement*, 98.

⁵⁰³ Cf. Soren Skovgaard Jensen, “On the National Origin of the Philosopher Boetius de Dacia,” *Classica et mediaevalia* 24 (1963): 232–41.

⁵⁰⁴ Cf. Jakob Hans Josef Schneider, “The eternity of the world Thomas Aquinas and Boethius of Dacia,” *Archives d'histoire doctrinale et littéraire du Moyen Age* (1999): 138.

⁵⁰⁵ Cf. James Athansius Weisheipl, “The Date and Context of Aquinas' *De Aeternitate Mundi*,” in *Essays in Ancient and Medieval Philosophy Presented to Joseph Owens, C.Ss.R.*, ed. Lloyd P. Gerson (Toronto: Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies, 1983), 245.

⁵⁰⁶ Cf. Malcolm de Mowbray, “1277 And All That — Students And Disputations,” *Traditio* 57 (2002): 217–238, and Malcolm de Mowbray, “The *De Aeternitate Mundi* of Boethius of Dacia and the Paris Condemnation of 1277,” *Recherches de Théologie Et Philosophie Médiévales* 73 (2006): 201–253.

⁵⁰⁷ Cf. Jean-Pierre Torrell, *Saint Thomas Aquinas: The Person and His Work*, trans. by Robert Royal (Washington, D.C: Catholic University of America Press, 2005); James Athanasius Weisheipl, *Friar Thomas D'Aquino: His Life, Thought, and Works: With Corrigenda and Addenda* (Washington, D.C: Catholic University of America Press, 1983).

⁵⁰⁸ Franz Pelster, “De Concordantia Dictorum Thomae: Ein Echtes Werk Aus des Letzten Lebesjahren des hl. Thomas von Aquin,” *Gregorianum*, 4 (1923): 72–105.

⁵⁰⁹ Cf. Thomas Bukovski, “An Early Dating for Aquinas' '*De Aeternitate Mundi*,’” *Gregorianum* (1970): 303.

The answer to Bukowski's challenge was given by many scholars.⁵¹⁰ Torrell, Wippel, and Weisheipl all rightly point out that Bukowski's analysis is flawed. Namely, it does not take into consideration the most apparent fact of *De Aeternitate Mundi* when compared to other of Thomas' works which mention eternity, which is that Thomas expounds the view of the possibility of eternal creation only in *De Aeternitate Mundi*, and in no other works. If *De Aeternitate Mundi* was an earlier work, one would expect Thomas to have the same position on the possibility of eternal creation in both of his *Summae*, and the *De Potentia*, which supposedly came after *De Aeternitate Mundi*. Also, the large similarity between *De Unitate Intellectu* (written in 1270) and *De Aeternitate Mundi* is not explained if one accepts Bukowski's chronology. Furthermore, the idea that Thomas waited twenty years to respond to Bonaventure is not really an issue. This is because, it is most likely not Bonaventure, but Peckham who Thomas was answering to, and in that case, he answered shortly after Peckham's initial accusation.

Thomas Aquinas' *De Aeternitate Mundi*

De Aeternitate Mundi starts by asserting that the eternity of the world with all its parts is not a true position because of the creed of the catholic faith. Nonetheless, Thomas asks a counterfactual question concerning the eternity of the world: Could God have created the world as eternal? Here he makes two distinctions.

If "eternal" implies something that always existed and is not caused by God, then this kind of eternity is impossible. He does not go into more detail here. However, it seems that this is rejected because of the essence-existence differentiation, which posits the actualisation or the "unification" of every essence to existence by the one whose essence is to exist. Therefore, everything that has being (i.e., that exists), must receive it from the being which most truly is.

Secondly, is there something intrinsically faulty in the idea of the creation of an eternal being? What is implied when one says that an eternal thing cannot be made? Thomas answers: Either an absence of a passive potentiality or a contradiction in terms.⁵¹¹ Because angels are not material, it seems that they either do not have passive potentiality, and thus are necessarily actual, or their passive potentiality is somehow coeternal with God. The second option is swiftly rejected by Thomas, without further clarification. From the belief that angels exist, Thomas concludes that

⁵¹⁰ Cf. Weisheipl, "The Date and Context," Wippel, "Did Thomas Aquinas;" Torrell, *Saint Thomas*, and Ermengildo Bertola "Tommaso d'Aquino e il problema dell'eternità del mondo," *Rivista di filosofia neo-scolastica* (1974): 312-355.

⁵¹¹ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 3. I will be citing Miller's translation according to the structure given by the translator. Namely, he divides *De Aeternitate Mundi* (which was written as a single *opuscula* and thus without further division into chapters) into twenty chapters.

God creates them without passive potentiality.⁵¹² This argumentation may be the weakest part of the whole treatise since it relies on the belief that God actually created angels (in a certain way). Be that as it may, angels are not actual in the same way that God is. Namely, in angels, the difference between essence and existence still exists, and so their essence still has a sort of passive potentiality to existence, whereas God's essence is his existence.

Here it may be worth pointing out the two different types of contradiction in *De Aeternitate Mundi*. The first is between the things which the propositions describe (e.g. God's activity and the creation of angels) and the second is between the propositions stated, without having in mind those things which they describe in the world (e.g. "being created by God" and "being eternal" taken as propositions).⁵¹³ Thomas remarks that some people think that God could make contradictories true, while others think that it is not possible. The first view, held by some "pious men," probably Peter Damian (1007–1072), is deemed not heretical, but false.⁵¹⁴ Then he deals with the contradiction in terms. Namely, is the proposition "X does not have a beginning in time" contradictory to the proposition "X was created by God"? Here one must agree with Bertola in asserting that "The whole question comes down to determining whether "being created by God" and "not being temporal" is contradictory".⁵¹⁵ If this is a contradiction, it is so either because the efficient cause precedes the effect temporally or because non-being (non-existence) precedes being (existence) in time.⁵¹⁶

The first of these, according to my interpretation of Thomas, is false because of four reasons. Firstly, the way God produces an effect is not similar to motion (i.e. in time) but rather like fire (i.e. instantaneously). In other words, the effect exists simultaneously with the cause; thus, no precedence in time is posited. Secondly, even those things which produce forms (like the Sun) do not precede their effects in time. More so is this true for God, who is the producer of substances. Thirdly, when the effect ceases to exist simultaneously with the cause, such a lack of simultaneity is because "something complementary to that cause is lacking."⁵¹⁷ However, nothing is missing from the supreme cause which is God, and therefore its effects are simultaneous with its existence. The fourth reason says that God having free will does not lessen His power to create

⁵¹²Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 4.

⁵¹³ Cf. Ian Wilks, "Aquinas on the Past Possibility of the World's Having Existed Forever," *The Review of Metaphysics* 48, no. 2 (1994): 307.

⁵¹⁴ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 5.

⁵¹⁵ Bertola, "Tommaso d'Aquino," 348. Translation of my own.

⁵¹⁶ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 6.

⁵¹⁷ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 112.

(cause) instantaneously. This is because free will in God does not presuppose deliberation, which would make the effect non-simultaneous.⁵¹⁸

Thomas then deals with the second half of the dilemma. Namely, the idea that eternal creation necessarily presupposes non-being preceding being in time. The first reason he gives against this view is a quote from Anselm of Canterbury (ca. 1033–1109) that asserts that creation *ex nihilo* does not imply temporal primacy of non-being. In other words, there was not a time when there was no being. An important thing to point out is that here time is understood in a relative, and not absolute sense. This means it does not exist as separate from the relative motions of created creatures but only insofar as there is motion. Secondly, if “creation out of nothing” is understood as “creation after nothing,” then a distinction between the order of time and order of nature has to be made. Thomas says that creation *ex nihilo* does not imply the order of time, but of nature and gives a particularly illuminating example of the Sun and the air.

If we assume that the Sun is eternal, then there was not a time in which the air was not made luminous by the Sun. However, had the Sun not existed, then the air would not be luminous, but dark. Therefore, no precedence of non-being to being in time is posited, but only precedence in nature. In order to better understand this, one must remember that in Aristotle’s metaphysics there exists only the differentiation between form and matter, where form is that which actualises the matter (makes the matter exist), and it does not make sense to ask about the being of this composite itself. In Thomas, alongside the matter-form differentiation, there is a difference between essence (“what a thing is,” which is form and matter for material things and solely form for immaterial) and being or existence. Therefore, the existence of angels, which are not matter-form composites, and their diversity from God cannot be explained without this Thomistic “double-layered” metaphysics, which makes God the sustainer of all being, whether material or not.⁵¹⁹

After this, Thomas refutes the idea that the created world is coeternal with God by using the Boethian distinction between being a-temporal (which corresponds to God) and being eternal in time (which corresponds to angels and heavenly bodies). In other words, creatures created eternal by God are only thus in time and not outside of it. In the end, Thomas gives two reasons against the actual existence of an infinite number of souls that supposedly follows accepting the eternity of the world. He says that, even if one accepts that the world is eternal, that does not mean that there should exist an eternal number of souls because God could have either created men

⁵¹⁸ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 12.

⁵¹⁹ Cf. Fernand Brunner, “Über die thomistische Lehre vom Ursprung der Welt,” *Zeitschrift für philosophische Forschung* H. 2 (1962): 256.

without souls or created the world eternally, but men only from a certain point.⁵²⁰ Lastly, Thomas regards the impossibility of an actual infinite not to have been proven: “Furthermore, it has not yet been demonstrated that God cannot cause an infinite number of things to exist simultaneously.”⁵²¹

Thomas develops a nuanced view on the question of the eternity of the world. On the one hand, he rejects the idea that the world is necessarily eternal (which would have been directly deemed heretical and contrary to reality); since that directly contradicts the Genesis account and makes God's efficient and final causality secondary to his creation. In this respect, he is similar to most other thirteenth century philosophers in giving a “defence” of the faith against Aristotle. However, Thomas believes that, although an eternally existing world is not necessary, it was certainly not impossible for God to have created it as such. He demonstrates this by rejecting all possible counterarguments that purport to show that God could not have created the world as eternal. Firstly, there is nothing lacking in God which would make God not be able to create an eternal world. Secondly, there is nothing contradictory in an eternal world being created by God. This is demonstrated by showing that eternal creation does not need to imply temporal precedence of the cause to the effect or of non-being to being. Therefore, even though the truth of faith teaches that the world was created as finite, there was no rational necessity to the way in which it was created. This is because it was a free choice of an absolutely free God. As regards the general character of the work, I agree with Aertsen⁵²² in saying that it is a philosophical work (*contra* Grijs),⁵²³ although it mentions the article of the faith at the beginning. This is because the main *crux* of the treatise is the incompatibility of two propositions (1. Being created by God, and 2. Being eternal), and not a theological question. Rather, the philosophical method is here used to explain the nuances and consequences of a theological belief, something that would fall under natural theology in scholasticism, and under philosophical theology in today's academic classification.

⁵²⁰ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 19.

⁵²¹ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 19.

⁵²² Cf. Jan Adrianus Aertsen, “The eternity of the world: The believing and the philosophical Thomas. Some comments,” in *The Eternity of the World in the Thought of Thomas Aquinas and his Contemporaries*, ed. J.B.M. Wissink (Leiden: Brill, 1990): 12–18.

⁵²³ Cf. Grijs, de Ferdinandus JA, “The Theological Character of Aquinas' ‘De Aeternitate Mundi,’” in *The Eternity of the World in the Thought of Thomas Aquinas and his Contemporaries*, ed. J.B.M. Wissink (Leiden: Brill, 1990), 1–8.

Boethius of Dacia's *De Aeternitate Mundi*

Boethius starts his treatise by asserting that it is foolish to seek rational argumentation for things that do not admit of it. It is equally problematic to believe something that admits rational investigation only through faith. Boethius' goal for this work is threefold: 1) to defend the Catholic faith, 2) to defend natural philosophy and 3) to show that there is no contradiction between faith and philosophy.

Boethius starts by giving eleven arguments that prove the world had a beginning in time. The first proposition states that the creation of the world must come after the existence of its cause. The second proposition is linked to the first. It simply states that, if the world were eternal, it would be coeternal with God, which is taken to be impossible. The third proposition rests on a hierarchy of causes. Namely, on the idea of the heavens as the causes of time in the world. However, since the heavenly bodies are finite, they cannot produce an infinite effect. Therefore, the world cannot be infinite. The fourth proposition starts by asserting that God is prior to the world by nature. Since nature and duration are the same in God, he must also be prior to the world by duration. Along with this, I think that Boethius holds the idea that God is absolutely simple, and therefore his attributes do not point to any real distinction in Him, but only a rational distinction in our minds.⁵²⁴ The fifth proposition asserts that, because creation *ex nihilo* implies priority of nature on the part of God, it must also imply temporal priority of God to its creation. Boethius does not supply further argumentation for this claim but gives us a tautology: “[T]o begin to be and to be eternal are mutually exclusive for one and the same thing.”⁵²⁵

The sixth proposition starts from the observation that, unlike infinity, previous time can be added on to. Since this is possible in our world, time that has passed cannot be infinite. The seventh proposition relies on the absurdity of an infinite number of past generations. More concretely, there would need to be an infinite number of any kind of animal, for there to be animals today. This argument is similar to the infinite number of passed moments that needed to be traversed up to the actual moment, which would amount to an absurdity. However, this argument is weaker, since it relies both on the absurdity of the infinity of past time and also on the equal infinity of the generation of animals and the world itself. The eighth proposition cites Aristotle's Sixth book of the *Physica* in which the Stagirite asserts the convertibility of magnitude, motion, and time. Following this, since magnitude is finite, the same must hold for motion and time. The ninth proposition is the famous argument for the finitude of the world from the infinity of actually

⁵²⁴ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 37.

⁵²⁵ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 38.

existing souls. Namely, since rational human souls are immortal, if the world were eternal in the past, then an infinite number of actually existing rational souls would have to exist at this moment. The tenth proposition is something that was already mentioned in the seventh proposition. It is a Bonaventurian argument from the impossibility of infinite previous moments having passed before arriving at the actuality of the current moment. Finally, the eleventh proposition states that everything which has a cause must also have a beginning. Because the world has a cause, it must also have a beginning.

After eleven arguments against the eternity of the world (a), Boethius gives five arguments for the possibility of an eternal creation (b), thirteen for the statement that it is actually the case that the world was created eternally (c). Boethius gives his solution followed by detailed answers to the last thirteen arguments, i.e. the position (c).⁵²⁶ The first argument for the possibility of an eternal world is that the first cause does not need to precede its effect in duration, but only in nature.⁵²⁷ The second argument, using Aristotle's example of a triangle that eternally has three sides, reinforces the first argument. Namely, even if something is eternally true, it does not follow that it cannot also be caused. The third argument is that of the Sun and the lucid air.⁵²⁸ The fourth argument is the same as the third, only the Augustinian variant with the eternal foot and its coeternal footprint. The fifth is from the comparison with the eternal future. Namely, as Christian doctrine teaches, the future of each individual is eternal. Therefore, if God could have made the future as eternal, there could be nothing preventing Him in making the past eternal as well. Now Boethius turns to the thirteen arguments that purport to show the world to have actually, and not just possibly, been created as eternal. The first argument can be summed up as follows:

1. Everything incorruptible is eternal,
2. Everything that is not generated is incorruptible,
3. The world is not generated, *ergo*
4. The world is incorruptible. (from 1, 2, 3), *ergo*
5. The world is eternal (from 1, 4).⁵²⁹

The second argument says that, since time is the measurement of motion, there could not have been any time before the world was made. Therefore, the world must be eternal. The third argument starts by asserting that the underlying principle of a thing's existence is matter. But, if

⁵²⁶ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 39.

⁵²⁷ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 40.

⁵²⁸ Cf. Thomas' argument in the previous chapter.

⁵²⁹ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 41.

the world was created in time, then there could not be any matter preceding it.⁵³⁰ The fourth says that, since every change requires a subject, matter, and a certain potency, and since creation *ex nihilo* could not involve any of these, the world must be eternal. The fifth argument states the impossibility of the world existing as soon as time “started” to be. In other words, “[T]hat which begins in any duration must come to be within a part of that duration.”⁵³¹ The sixth argument starts from the process of generation and corruption. Since every generation follows upon corruption, and every corruption necessitates a prior generation, there could not have been a “first” generation, since corruption would have needed to precede it. The seventh argument is the argument from the absolute sufficiency of the first cause. Boethius sums up this argument exquisitely:

“A being which is eternal both in terms of its substance and in terms of its every disposition, to which nothing is added in the future and from which nothing is lacking in the past of that whereby it would produce its effect, produces its immediate effect as coeternal to itself.”⁵³²

The eighth argument goes like this: Because God had the power and the will to act in order to create the world from eternity, and because every agent that has the power and the will to act to create an effect does so, God did create the world as coeternal to himself. The ninth argument states that since every new effect requires something new on the part of its principles, and since nothing new can be added to the supreme cause that is God, all his effects must be coeternal with Him.⁵³³ The tenth argument tries to prove the necessity of the first mover being eternal in motion by saying that all other motions depend on the first, and since an *ad infinitum* series of causes is impossible, the first cause must be eternal in motion. The eleventh argument states that every postponed willing awaits for something. However, the divine will did not have to await for anything to create. His effects are not postponed and, therefore, are coeternal with Him. The twelfth argument is in line with the seventh onward. Namely, between the first cause and its creation there couldn’t have been time or eternity. Therefore, the cause and its effect must be eternal. We might say that the thirteenth and final argument is a summary of the last group of arguments. It states that every effect must be preceded by change, and since there was no time before the *ex nihilo* creation, there could not have been change either. As conclusion, creation must be understood as eternal.

⁵³⁰ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 42.

⁵³¹ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 42.

⁵³² Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 42.

⁵³³ Cf. Thomas' argument of similar nature above.

Before the solution and the answers to the thirteen arguments for the eternity of the world, Boethius presents an interesting *intermezzi* in his argumentation. This is my reconstruction of the argumentation that Boethius lays down before his solution:

Thesis 1) The effect of an eternal cause does not need to be coeternal with it since the eternal cause could have willed to create his effect in time.⁵³⁴

Contra Thesis 1) (1): Since *Thesis 1)* relies on inferring about the reasons behind the actions of the divine cause, it is just as probable to suggest that the divine cause willed to create its effect eternally.

Contra Thesis 1) (2) If God willed from eternity to create the world in a certain temporal moment, then He would not be able to create it at another time. This is unacceptable with regards to God's omnipotence and freedom of will.

Thesis 2) The idea that God eternally willed to create the world at a certain moment does not lessen his omnipotence or freedom of will. This is because God was open to eternally willing the temporal creation of the world at any given moment in time, but He chose a certain moment in time, thus necessarily eliminating the possibility of temporal creation in all other temporal moments.

Contra Thesis 2) (1) God could not have been open to eternally will any certain moment for the creation of the world since God's will is eternal and unchangeable.

Contra Thesis 2) (2) For every effect, there needs to be change, either in the agent or in the subject. Since there could be no change in the divine will and since there is no proper subject of creation before the creation itself, creation needs to be understood eternally.⁵³⁵

Contra Thesis 1) (3) Every new effect requires some change, in at least one of three ways: 1) In the one who wills, 2) in the subject willed, or 3) in the moment coming to pass. In the creation *ex nihilo* neither of the three requirements are met. Namely, the divine will cannot change (1), the subject of the divine will does not properly exist (2), and since there is no time before creation, the moment cannot come to pass (3). Therefore, since every effect requires some change, and since temporal creation does not involve change, it is impossible that an eternal being willed from eternity to create in a certain moment in time.

At the end of this exposition, Boethius adds that these arguments are those that the heretics use to prove that the world is eternal and thus they contradict the Christian faith. Precisely because of this, it is important to know how to answer them, and this is what Boethius will do after the Solution.⁵³⁶

⁵³⁴ Boethius of Dacia, On the Eternity of the World, 45.

⁵³⁵ Boethius of Dacia, On the Eternity of the World, 45.

⁵³⁶ Boethius of Dacia, On the Eternity of the World, 47.

Boethius starts the Solution by asserting the importance and legitimacy of philosophy. Because philosophy deals with all types of being (natural, mathematical, and divine), and because all that is part of being can be determined by arguments, philosophy must deal with everything that falls under the scope of argumentation. He adds a strong word against those that would like to limit the scope of philosophy and philosophers.⁵³⁷ The main claim of the Solution is that none of the three “disciplines” of philosophy can in fact show by argumentation that the first motion and the world was created. Boethius lays down two important presuppositions. The first one concerns those claims that any one kind of science can make. Namely, anything that “one that does science” (*facit scientiam*) can “prove, concede, or deny,”⁵³⁸ he can do only within the principles of his own science (*principiis suae scientiae*).⁵³⁹ The second important presupposition is that the results of natural philosophy are not absolute, but are nevertheless true within the scope of natural principles.

After giving these two important caveats, Boethius intends to show why neither of the three types of philosophers can show that the world had a beginning in time. Within the scope of natural principles, the natural philosopher cannot prove that the world had a beginning. Boethius spends the most time on this, and less time on the inability of the mathematicians and the metaphysicians of doing the same. Firstly, every change in motion requires the previous motion as its cause. However, for the first motion to exist, it - *per definitionem* - cannot be preceded by a previous motion. This goes against the principles of natural philosophy and is something that a natural philosopher cannot prove. Secondly, change in the effect requires novelty in one of its principles. But, the novelty in the principles cannot be posited without change in the principles. Therefore, nature cannot produce change without previous change. But, since an actually existing series of changers *ad infinitum* is impossible, there still needs to be a first cause. That is why Aristotle concludes that the first motion must be eternal. What follows from the first two arguments is that the natural philosopher cannot deal with creation. Namely, nature produces all its effects from a subject and from matter. This production is called generation and is the proper object of natural philosophy. On the other hand, creation *ex nihilo* does not involve neither matter nor a subject. Creation does not fall under the scope of natural principles, and since each science can only deal

⁵³⁷ Boethius of Dacia, On the Eternity of the World, 47.

⁵³⁸ Boethius of Dacia, On the Eternity of the World, 47.

⁵³⁹ In my reading of Boethius of Dacia, “science” (*scientia*) is a part of philosophy, which is why the natural philosopher is also called the “one who does science.” This *scientia* is understood as a series of truth-claims which rely on first principles and subsequent deductive argumentation. The difference between, e.g. the natural sciences (that are done by the natural philosopher) and theology (which is also taken by Boethius to be a science, different from the catholic faith itself) is that natural sciences rely on first principles which are demonstrable (such as mathematical truths). Theology, on the other hand, takes its first principles from the articles of faith, which are not demonstrable. However, all the subsequent “truths” of theology are thought to be deduced by the same procedure as in other sciences.

with those things which pertain to its own principles, natural philosophy cannot explain creation. Natural philosophy is also unable to explain the existence of the first man,⁵⁴⁰ since the first man was created, and not generated.⁵⁴¹ What should a natural philosopher say about those teachings of the Catholic faith that are not demonstrable within his own science? As long as they are not contrary to the principles of his science and do not “destroy” his science, he should not deny them. Boethius takes the Catholic teaching of the resurrection of every man after death as an example. According to the principles of nature, something corrupted cannot be generated again as numerically the same. Therefore, the natural philosopher claims that the resurrection of man after death is not possible according to the natural principles.

Boethius holds that both the natural philosopher and the believer are right in asserting their claims. The natural philosopher can claim that, according to the principles of nature, it is impossible that numerically the same man would be resurrected. The believer can claim that this is possible through a supernatural cause. Thus, there is no contradiction between the two claims, and the so-called theory of double truth⁵⁴² is not claimed in this text (*contra* the 1277 Condemnation). The same logic applies to the question of the eternity of the world.⁵⁴³ After giving a detailed account as to why a natural philosopher 1) cannot prove that the world is eternal and 2) does not contradict faith, Boethius goes to show that the same is true for the mathematician and the metaphysician. The metaphysician cannot establish neither that the world is eternal or finite. This is because all such reasoning presupposes the knowledge of the free intention of the divine will:

“To say that the metaphysician could demonstrate this is not only like a figment [of the imagination] but is, in my opinion, akin to madness. From whence does this reasoning come to man, by which he might perfectly investigate the divine will?”⁵⁴⁴

Boethius’ reasoning is against those that would like to rationally prove the finitude of the world, but also those that reason in favour of the eternity of the world. Boethius’ maxim is clear: There are truths of the Catholic faith which one needs to hold but cannot rationally prove. One of these is that the world was created as finite.

⁵⁴⁰ In the translation used, John F. Wippel uses the term “man.” However, the term used in the original is “homo” which can mean both man and human. The first created (according to the book of Genesis) is man, so that must have been the reason why Wippel translated it in such a way. Linked with this Here, it seems that Boethius writes about the creation of the first human, which is taken to be Adam.

⁵⁴¹ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 50.

⁵⁴² What Bianchi calls the “Mostro che si chiama ‘teoria della doppia verità’” (Monster which is called ‘the theory of double truth’], cf. Bianchi, *L’errore*, 180.

⁵⁴³ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 53.

⁵⁴⁴ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 54.

Sophistical, dialectical, and demonstrative argumentation should not be used where they do not yield concrete results. Rather, one should accept that there are parts of the law (i.e. the Christian faith) that are non-demonstrable, which is precisely what makes it a creed, and not a science. Although Boethius intends to answer all the three different types of arguments given above (1. For the temporal creation of the world, 2. For the possibility of the eternal creation of the world, and 3. For the actual eternal creation of the world), he only gives the answers to the position that the world was created as eternal (3).

As regards the first argument, Boethius lays down the distinction between “incorruptibility” taken narrowly and broadly. Understood narrowly, it involves those things whose matter does not undergo corruption. In this sense, we might say that the world is incorruptible, and thus eternal. However, if “incorruptibility” is understood broadly as that which can exist without being caused to be by another, it does not apply to the world. This is because, the eternal world is caused and kept in being by God, who is the only being that is incorruptible in the broad sense, because it is not kept in being by another. Boethius calls the keeping in being the principle of conservation. Replying to the second argument, Boethius attacks the idea of the eternal being as “that which admits of no duration before itself,”⁵⁴⁵ because, although there is no time before the world, there is [divine] eternity. Furthermore, he disagrees that a being which is preceded by eternity cannot exist. Suppose the world is actually eternal, says Boethius. Then, if a being will start existing in three days, before that happens, the whole of eternity will have to be traversed. Nonetheless, it does not make sense to say that this being would not exist.⁵⁴⁶ Boethius does not delve into why this *non sequitur* is in fact impossible. My interpretation is that he relies on the fact of experience. Namely, we see new beings being generated and existing, and that would be the case even if the world were eternal. Therefore, every new generation does not presuppose the necessity of traversing the whole of eternity.

Boethius replies to the third argument by stating that, although there was no matter before creation, there was a different type of potency. This potency (*potentia*) is in the agent (God), because He needed to have this to create the world. His reply to the fourth argument is that change is necessary for generation, but not creation. Against the fifth argument, Boethius clears up the terminology by stating that the world was not created *in* time, but *with* time, thus dispelling the objection that the world could not have started when time started. As a response to the sixth argument, Boethius rejects the principle which states that every corruption is preceded by a generation, because this would negate the possibility of the existence of a first man. According to

⁵⁴⁵ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 60.

⁵⁴⁶ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 60.

natural causes, this principle is correct. However, in light of creation, this principle cannot be defended. Boethius' response to the seventh argument is similar to the sixth. Namely, he grants the principle that every new effect follows from something that is missing in the agent. This he only grants partially, concerning natural causes and effects. God, as a supernatural cause, can create out of his free will. To the eighth argument, Boethius answers that the prerequisites of action existed in God, but only at the moment of creation, and not before. Thus, there is no necessity in God's creation, since it is limited to the moment of creation. To the ninth argument, Boethius answers that there does not need to be a new principle in every cause of an effect, but only in natural causes. This is because non-natural causes have free wills, which can decide despite their natural principles (or lack thereof).

To answer the tenth argument, Boethius denies that every motion must start in an eternal motion. Rather, every motion must start in a first motion that does not necessarily need to be eternal. In the eleventh argument, Boethius argues against the idea that, if God decided to create the world temporally, then there would have needed to be postponement in the will. Boethius says that this is correct for a will in time. However, since the eternal will is outside time, postponement that includes duration does not apply. Boethius rejects the conclusion of the twelfth argument. Namely, because there cannot be time or eternity between God and creation, creation has to be coeternal with God. This is rejected using the Boethian distinction between the eternal now, and the a-temporal now.⁵⁴⁷ As regards the thirteenth argument, Boethius asserts that positing an intention in God to create the world in a certain moment in time is not sophistical, because not everything that cannot be rationally demonstrated is a figment of imagination.⁵⁴⁸ Against the thirteenth argument, Boethius states that the necessity of change prior to every effect does not apply to the divine will.

Afterwards, he again asserts that both the arguments for and against the eternity of the world are sophistical. At the end, Boethius asserts his teaching on the difference between philosophy and Revelation. He uses the teaching on the Resurrection of man, which is impossible according to the Philosopher, but true according to the Catholic faith. However, they are both in the right, since it is in fact impossible to prove this according only to natural causes, and thus a supernatural cause is needed.

⁵⁴⁷ Here I am referring to the early medieval Boethius, Anicius Manlius Severinus Boethius (d.524). He makes this distinction in the Fifth Book of his *De Consolatione Philosophiae*.

⁵⁴⁸ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 64.

Conclusion

In the Conclusion, I will give the answers to the proposed research questions given in the Introduction, based on the analyses of the primary sources in the main part of the paper.

The first question was: “Can philosophy prove that the world was created in time?”

Thomas rejects this possibility. He does this by showing that creation does not necessarily suggest a temporal precedence neither of cause to effect, nor of non-being to being. Furthermore, Thomas thinks that the argument against the actually existing infinity of souls is inconclusive, and therefore does not prove the finiteness of the world.

Boethius also rejects this possibility, but in a slightly different way. Namely, Boethius thinks that no *scientia*⁵⁴⁹ (and thus also no natural philosophy) can inquire into the ways in which God created the world. This, then, excludes both the philosophical arguments for the eternity and for the finiteness of the world. What natural philosophy can prove is only that, within the principles of nature, God could not have created the world as finite. This statement is in fact correct, even under the scope of theology.

The second question was: “Could God have created the world as eternal?”

For Thomas the answer to this question is positive. By rejecting all the possible counter arguments for the opposite position, Thomas arrives at the conclusion that it was possible for God to have created the world as eternal, although He did not do so. Therefore, by imploring the philosophical method, Thomas gives an affirmative answer to this question.

On the other hand, Boethius does not touch on this question directly. Instead, he takes an agnostic stance on the matter. Namely, the will of God, in the process of creation is not knowable to humans. That being said, one who believes knows by faith (because God revealed it to humanity) that God did in fact create the world as finite. Reasonings, both for and against the possibility of the world being created as eternal, are deemed “sophistical and weak” by Boethius. Therefore, I believe that the contrafactual question posed by Thomas would be deemed “sophistical” by Boethius of Dacia.

⁵⁴⁹ Cf. fn. 59.

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